

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: RAMALINGAM RAMA****FIRST NAME: KRISHNAA****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Prof. CLEENEWERCK**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)
The author uses Zotero to insert references
The author used the following software: (Microsoft Word 2010 on Windows 10)

ESSENTIALS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

It is popularly said “*a work well planned is half well executed.*” This suits well to the subject “International Academic Writing” being laid as a foundation course to the doctoral studies. The course pack (ACA-401D Period 1) outlines the professionalism and discipline that is expected from a student to submit a fair response paper in accordance with international writing rules/techniques. The whole idea behind this paper is to bring students from various geographies under one umbrella of learning and discipline by insisting use of common template which results in uniformity besides enhancing the quality in learning. The style to be deployed in writing, punctuations, how to spell check, how to use a comma, sets right the basics of the students. It is a complete overhauling exercise for students to remember what they forgot from the school days. The student is clearly put on a perfect square where he needs to study and research. The student knows clearly how to write, what to write and how to present it.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The first topic of the course pack is Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 2-5). The essentials of essay writing are outlined below:

- (a) analyzing the question and defining the key terms
- (b) form a point of view
- (c) research the topic
- (d) substantiate your view by proper evidence

- (e) take notes from the selected readings or research materials
- (f) write an essay plan and organize the ideas
- (g) the first draft to contain introduction, body and conclusion
- (h) read the draft more than two times (correct wherever required)
- (i) edit and redraft the essay, till it becomes clear and conveys your viewpoint
- (j) have a family member or friends to read it
- (k) quote references and bibliography
- (l) do not forget to thank those supported you on the task (acknowledge the same)
- (m) submit the final draft

3) PREVENING PLAGIARISM

Excerpts of page no.5 of the coursepack are reproduced below:

“All academic essays MUST contain references. Referencing guards against plagiarism, a serious academic offence.”

The importance of references is dealt here (EUCLID 2019, 5). References, acknowledges and respects the work of the author. It avoids claims of copyright infringement. Using information for research and educational purposes are legal defenses/exemptions to copyright infringement in many jurisdictions. But to avoid any legal action it is advisable to acknowledge the author and his work. This is not only a legal requirement but more of a moral requirement too.

Plagiarism is found rooted from the good olden days. Some famous quotes are mentioned below:

“People seldom improve when they have no model but themselves to copy after.”
(Oliver Goldsmith, www.goodreads.com)

“Intentionally using the quotes of others without author attribution is plagiarism and contributes to illiteracy.” (Rain Bojangles, www.goodreads.com)

The coursepack further discusses the importance of keeping the essay well organized and fairly complete in all respects. General advisories such as timely submission of assignments is stressed in the coursepack (EUCLID 2019, 5). The coursework commences from the basics of writing essay, cautions against plagiarism and finally advents into presentation.

4) APPRAISAL ON PRESENTATION

Page nos. 6-42 covers presentation which provides useful guidance on proper submission of responses. Usually such course packs will be mostly in the document format with instructions and guidelines advising the students about the rules of submission. But this course pack is well built with information in document form from pages 1-5 and then into presentation format to involve the students more attentively to understand the crucial aspects of writing and research. This idea bringing out a course pack with mixed combination of document and presentation is well intended by EUCLID to engage the students in reading the course material of 83 pages without any boredom. The presentation prescribes the students to save their papers in the format desired by EUCLID (e.g., Tamer Bahloul MED-677 FE.doc). In-text citation is also advised by which the source of the information is clearly disclosed in the paper (EUCLID 2019, 16). The paper while advising on the use of quotations, cautions the student that overuse of quotations will give an impression that the student has relied more on other source of information and it does not contain information or research of his own. Quotations should be used limitedly and only to persuade the reader about the researcher's viewpoint. Paraphrasing is also explained well through examples. Students are advised to avoid using contractions such as "can't or "won't" in the paper (EUCLID 2019, 39).

The thumb rules of writing papers are found in page nos.43-45 of the course pack. These are concise information provided in a nutshell for writing the paper effectively.

This was followed by the Euclid University {Consortium} – LIT-101 review which provides insights into how to use commas, punctuations and general advice on framing sentences. It proposes to use active voice unless passive voice is required (EUCLID 2019, 46).

Injunction is given not to begin sentence with a conjunction. At the same time, it is permitted to use a conjunction purposefully and appropriately which can be a powerful rhetorical or stylistic tool (EUCLID 2019, 50).

5) NEED OF STYLE GUIDES

A style guide is a means of documenting the approach of a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent. In order to ensure consistency in writing styles guidelines are usually published by organizations. The undersigned has read the Strunk's "The Elements of Style" and "BBC News style guide" which will serve as an invaluable tool to maintain a uniform style in writing.

Other reference materials include Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996 (both published by the University of Chicago Press) and MLA Handbook (EUCLID 2019, 70).

Apart from the above reference materials prescribed in the course pack, the undersigned also noticed in search that APA Style Guide to electronic references would also be relatively useful in quoting electronic documents in the research work in case of non-availability of the author. It advises to mention the Uniform Source Locator of the electronic document in such cases.

For table preparation, the publication manual of the American Psychological Association has been recommended (EUCLID 2019, 74). Latin abbreviations and expressions are provided for usage in footnotes.

6) CONCLUSION

Writing skills are equally important as oratory skills for a legal professional. The writing skills of a legal professional are expected to be precise and sharp. My present duties in work involves drafting and review of pleadings, counter affidavits, legal notices and preparing presentations. This coursepack is a perfect guide to improve my writing and presentation skills. If course pack is considered a ship in which the student sails, the teachings of the instructor is the lighthouse to show the correct direction in sailing (learning). The guidance of the instructors will certainly enable me to complete the doctoral studies and meet the expectations of EUCLID.

I am confident that the subject of International Academic Writing will certainly improve my overall confidence and ability to write clearly, yet simpler, conveying the point with clarity. To conclude I am certain that this learning will be of immense use throughout my academic and professional career.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2019. *ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*.

American Psychological Association. 2007. *APA Style Guide to Electronic References*. Compiled by Susan Herman, Editorial Supervisor: Anne Hill.

William Strunk. 2011. *The Elements of Style*. Edited by Chris Hong. The Elements of Style Press.

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